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Research Article

**THE ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF
OFLOXACIN & TINIDAZOLE BY USING RP- HPLC****P. Valli Sowjanya^{1*}, Santanu Kumar Hotta², Chaitanya Bangari³,
Dr.M.B.Venkatapathi Raju⁴**¹Avanthi Institute Of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Vizianagaram, AP-531162**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

The present work deals with ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF OFLOXACIN AND TINIDAZOLE IN TABLETS BY RP-HPLC using INERTSIL ODS 3V column, C18(250x4.6 ID). A mobile phase consisting of phosphate buffer: Acetonitrile buffer, pH 3.5 adjusted using Orthophosphoric acid in 50:50v/v ratio was employed in this study. The flow rate was set at 1.2 ml/min. Separation was performed at ambient temperature. Eluents were monitored by UV detector set at 308nm. The developed method was statistically validated for linearity and range, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantification, accuracy, robustness, Ruggedness and specificity.

Keywords: phosphate buffer, Acetonitrile, linearity, range, precision, limit of detection, limit of quantification, accuracy, robustness, Ruggedness and specificity.

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INTRODUCTION:

A synthetic fluoroquinolone (fluoroquinolones) antibacterial agent that inhibits the supercoiling activity of bacterial DNA gyrase, halting DNA replication. Ofloxacin acts on DNA gyrase and topoisomerase IV, enzymes which, like human topoisomerase, prevents the excessive supercoiling of DNA during replication or transcription. By inhibiting their function, the drug thereby inhibits normal cell division.

Tinidazole is a prodrug and antiprotozoal agent. The nitro group of tinidazole is reduced in *Trichomonas* by a ferredoxin-mediated electron transport system. The free nitro radical generated as a result of this reduction is believed to be responsible for the antiprotozoal activity. It is suggested that the toxic free radicals covalently bind to DNA, causing DNA damage and leading to cell death. The mechanism by which tinidazole exhibits activity against *Giardia* and *Entamoeba* species is not known.

The concept of analytical chemistry lies in the precise and accurate measurements. This determination requires highly sophisticated instruments and methods like HPLC, gas chromatography, HPTLC, spectrophotometry, fluorimetry etc. Instrumental methods are sensitive, accurate, precise and desirable for regular determination of drugs in formulations, thereby is advantageous than the conventional volumetric methods. On the literature survey it was found that Ofloxacin and Tinidazole was estimated independently and in combination with other drugs by several chromatographic, spectrometric methods in pharmaceutical formulations and in biological samples [1].

In view of the need analytical method in the quality control laboratories for routine analysis of Ofloxacin and Tinidazole in formulations, the present work aims to develop simple and accurate instrumental methods for simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Tinidazole and extend it for their determination in formulation and in laboratory prepared synthetic mixture [2].

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY:**Instruments used**

UV-Visible Spectrophotometer	Nicolet evolution 100
UV-Visible Spectrophotometer software	Vwereion Pro
HPLC software	Spin chrome (LC SOLUTIONS)
HPLC	Shimadzu(LC 20 AT VP)
Ultra sonicator	Citizen, Digital Ultrasonic Cleaner
pH meter	Global digital
Electronic balance	Shimadzu
Syringe	Hamilton
HPLC Column	Inertsil ODS 3V(250x4.6mm) 5µm

Reagents used

Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate	HPLC Grade
Potassium Hydrogen Phosphate	AR Grade
Acetonitrile	HPLC Grade
Phosphate Buffer	AR Grade
Methanol	HPLC Grade

Drugs used

Ofloxacin and Tinidazole drugs	Gift Samples obtained from Chandra labs, Hyd.
Oriflox TZ (200+600) (Ofloxacin-200 mg Tinidazole-600 mg label claims).	Obtained from local pharmacy

Mobile Phase:[3]

A mixture of 50 volumes of 20mM Phosphate buffer pH 3.5: 50 volumes of Acetonitrile. The mobile phase were sonicated for 10 min to remove gases.

Preparation of Buffer:

2.72gm. of potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer were weighed and dissolved in 100ml of water and volume were made up to 1000ml with water. Adjust the pH to 3.5 using ortho phosphoric acid. The buffer were filtered through 0.45µ filters to remove all fine particles and gases

Standard solution:

weigh accurately 50 mg of Ofloxacin and 150 mg of Tinidazole in 100 ml of volumetric flask and dissolve in 10ml of mobile phase and make up the volume with mobile phase. From above stock solution 50 µg/ml of Ofloxacin and 150 µg/ml of Tinidazole is prepared by diluting 1ml to 10ml with mobile phase. This solution is used for recording chromatogram.

ASSAY [4-10]**Preparation of samples for Assay****Standard sample**

weigh accurately 50 mg of Ofloxacin and 150 mg of Tinidazole in 100 ml of volumetric flask and

$$\% \text{ Assay} = \frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{DS} \times \frac{DT}{WT} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \frac{AW}{LC} \times 100$$

Where,

AS: Average peak area due to standard preparation

AT: Peak area due to assay preparation

WS: Weight of Ofloxacin/ Tinidazole in mg

WT: Weight of sample in assay preparation

DT: Dilution of assay preparation

dissolve in 10ml of mobile phase and make up the volume with mobile phase. From above stock solution 50 µg/ml of Ofloxacin and 150 µg/ml of Tinidazole is prepared by diluting 1ml to 10ml with mobile phase. This solution is used for recording chromatogram.

Sample:

10 Tablets (each Tablet contains 50 mg of Ofloxacin and 150 mg of Tinidazole) were weighed and taken into a mortar uniformly mixed. Test stock solutions of 50 µg/ml of Ofloxacin and 150 µg/ml of Tinidazole was prepared by dissolving weight equivalent to 50 mg of Ofloxacin and 150 mg of Tinidazole and dissolved in sufficient mobile phase. After that filtered the solution using 0.45-micron syringe filter and Sonicated for 5 min and dilute to 100ml with mobile phase. Further dilutions are prepared in 5 replicates of 50 µg/ml of Ofloxacin and 150 µg/ml of Tinidazole was made by adding 1 ml of stock solution to 10 ml of mobile phase.

Calculation

The amount of Ofloxacin and Tinidazole present in the formulation by using the formula given below, and results shown in above table:

Chromatographic trials for simultaneous estimation of Povidone and Ornidazole by RP- HPLC

	Trail -1	Trail 2	Trail 3	Trail 4	Trail 5 optimised method
Mobile phase	KH ₂ PO ₄ +K ₂ HPO ₄ +A CN(55:45) pH 6.9	KH ₂ PO ₄ :ACN (60:40) pH 3.5	Phosphate Buffer:ACN (40:60) pH:6.0	Phosphate buffer:ACN I(45:55) pH: 6.5	Phosphate buffer:ACN(45:55) pH: 6.5
Diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent	Mobile phase was used as the diluent
Flow rate	1.2 ml/min	1.2 ml/min	1.2 ml/min	1.2 ml/min	1.2 ml/min
Column	Inertsil ODS (250*4.6 mm, 5µm)	Inertsil ODS (250*4.6 mm, 5µm)	Inertsil ODS (250*4.6 mm, 5µm)	Inertsil ODS (250*4.6 mm, 5µm)	Inertsil ODS (250*4.6 mm, 5µm)
Detector wavelength	308nm	308 nm	308 nm	308nm	240nm
Column oven	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient	Ambient
Injection volume	20µL/min	20µl	20µl	20µl	20µl
Running time	5min	6 min	10min	8min	8min

Validation parameters such as specificity, Linearity, Range, Accuracy, Precision, Repeatability, Intermediate Precision, Detection Limit, Quantitation Limit, Robustness also studied [5-10].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:**Method development trials:****Trial 1:**

Chromatogram of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase
Result for Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
1	Ofloxacin	4.393	1032.537	4357	0.773	--
2	Tinidazole	4.660	495.024	3333	2.063	0.905

Observation: The draw back of this trial is tailing factor of Ofloxacin is less than 0.9. The Tailing factor of Tinidazole is 2.0. The resolution between the peaks is less than 1.5.

Trial 2:

Chromatogram of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase
Result for Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
1	Ofloxacin	2.610	1401.415	637	2.180	--
2	Tinidazole	3.680	1591.804	2007	1.865	2.884

Observation:

The Efficiency was not satisfactory for Ofloxacin. The tailing factor of Ofloxacin is not within the limits. Hence it was not taken for optimization.

Trial 3:

Fig. 8.3.3: Chromatogram of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase
Result for Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
1	Tinidazole	3.493	829.134	3005	1.000	--
2	Ofloxacin	4.350	4531.052	1770	1.929	2.563

Observation: The resolution between peaks was less than 1.5. The Theoretical plates of Ofloxacin is less than 2000. Hence it was not taken for optimization.

Trial 4:

Chromatogram of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase
Result for Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
1	Ofloxacin	3.457	5358.855	2586	1.765	--
2	Tinidazole	4.100	2641.258	1247	2.673	1.747

Observation:

The Efficiency was not satisfactory for Tinidazole i.e., less than 2000. The tailing factor of Tinidazole was more than 2.0. Hence it was not taken for optimization.

Trial 5:

Chromatogram of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase
Result for Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by using mobile phase

S.no	Name	Rt	Area	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution
1	Ofloxacin	2.200	2071.597	3078	1.524	--
2	Tinidazole	3.727	5715.723	5058	1.250	8.292

Observation:

The no of theoretical plates of Ofloxacin and Tinidazole were more than 2000. The tailing factor of Ofloxacin and Tinidazole was less than 2.0. Resolution between the peaks was more than 1.5. All the system suitability parameters were satisfied. Hence this method was optimised

ASSAY

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-1

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-2

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-3

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-4

Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation-5

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-1

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-2

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-3

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-4

Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation-5

Ofloxacin			Tinidazole	
Standard Area	1	2065.577		5719.328
	2	2079.612		5727.731
	3	2074.141		5707.874
	4	2061.145		5692.065
	5	2041.664		5681.072
	Average	2073.110	Average	5705.614
Sample area	1	2090.572		5748.239
	2	2094.040		5712.922
	3	2068.688		5760.567
	4	2090.572		5748.239
	5	2069.791		5760.567
	Average	2082.733	Average	5746.107
Tablet average weight		924	mg	924
Standard weight		50	mg	150
Sample weight		231	mg	231
Label amount		200	mg	600
std.purity		99.6		99.7
Cal.:		200.12	mg	602.45
	%Assay	100.06	%	100.41

VALIDATION OF RP – HPLC METHOD

Specificity:

There is no interference of mobile phase, solvent and placebo with the analyte peak and also the peak purity of analyte peak which indicate that the method is specific for the analysis of analytes in their dosage form.

Blank chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase

Standard chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-1

Standard chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-2

Standard chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-3

Sample chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-1

Sample chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-2

Sample chromatogram for specificity by using mobile phase-3

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

LOD and LOQ of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin were calculated mathematically. The LOD of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin was found to be 1.92 μ g/mL and 5.86 μ g/mL. The LOQ of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin was found to be 5.81 μ g/mL and 17.75 μ g/mL respectively

Precision:

Precision of method was demonstrated by

- Intraday precision
- Inter day precision

Method precision:

Ofloxacin		
S.No.	Rt	Area
1	2.213	2051.034
2	2.190	2022.249
3	2.210	2062.991
4	2.203	2052.703
5	2.210	2039.124
6	2.203	2058.026
avg	2.2048	2047.688
stdev	0.0083	14.818
%RSD	0.38	0.72

Tinidazole		
S.No.	Rt	Area
1	3.740	5647.876
2	3.710	5587.585
3	3.733	5692.900
4	3.727	5709.739
5	3.740	5765.096
6	3.733	5740.309
Avg	3.731	5690.584
Stdev	0.011	64.544
%RSD	0.30	1.13

Chromatogram of precision -3

Chromatogram of precision -6**Accuracy**

To study the reliability, suitability and accuracy of the method, recovery studies were carried out. To an equivalent quantity of formulation powder, a known quantity of standard Tinidazole and Ofloxacin were added to 80% and 120% level extracted with mobile phase and made up to mark with same. This solution was further diluted. The concentration of drugs present in resulting solution was determined using assay method and percentage recovery and % RSD were calculated.

Chromatogram of Accuracy 80% level-1

Chromatogram of Accuracy 80% level-2

Chromatogram of Accuracy 80% level-3

Chromatogram of Accuracy 100% level-1

Chromatogram of Accuracy 100% level-2

Chromatogram of Accuracy 100% level-3

Chromatogram of Accuracy 120% level-1

Chromatogram of Accuracy 120% level-2

Chromatogram of Accuracy 120% level-3

Table: 7.3.3. Recovery Studies

Recovery	Ofloxacin					
	Amount taken mcg/ml	Area	Average area	Amount recovered	% recovery	Average recovery
80%	50	2271.034	2269.511	49.07	98.14	99.12 %
	50	2262.991				
	50	2274.509				
100%	60	2503.471	2500.433	59.77	99.61	
	60	2495.284				
	60	2502.545				
120%	70	2763.590	2774.247	69.74	99.63	
	70	2795.559				
	70	2763.591				

Recovery	Ofloxacin					
	Amount taken mcg/ml	Area	Average area	Amount recovered	% recovery	Average recovery
80%	150	6197.876	6195.850	147.27	98.18	98.71%
	150	6192.900				
	150	6196.773				
100%	180	6839.037	6900.456	179.01	99.45	
	180	6893.245				
	180	6969.086				
120%	210	7641.702	7652.138	206.85	98.50	
	210	7662.413				
	210	7652.300				

Linearity and Range

Tinidazole and Ofloxacin were found to be linear in the range of 60-140 μ g/mL. Calibration graphs were plotted using peak areas of standard drugs vs. concentration of standard solutions, fig. below. The slope, intercept and correlation coefficient values were found to be 15.529, 308.49, and 0.9966 respectively for Tinidazole and 8.2153, 53.349 and 0.9965 respectively for Ofloxacin.

Chromatogram of Linearity solution-1**Chromatogram of Linearity solution-4**

Chromatogram of Linearity solution-5

Calibration data of Tinidazole and Ofloxacin by RP-HPLC

Tinidazole	
mcg	Area
90	4338.795
120	5048.486
150	5782.167
180	6658.847
210	7541.702

Calibration graph of Tinidazole by RP-HPLC.

Ofloxacin	
mcg	Area
30	1571.372
40	1849.991
50	2091.759
60	2386.795
70	2663.590

Calibration Graph of Ofloxacin by RP-HPLC

Robustness

1. In order to demonstrate the robustness of the method, the following optimized conditions were slightly varied.
2. ± 2 ml/min in flow rate, fig. 7.3.19-7.3.20.
3. ± 2 units in wavelength, fig. 7.3.21-7.3.22.

The response factors for these changed chromatographic parameters were almost same as that of the fixed chromatographic parameters and hence developed method is said to be robust.

Robustness (change in flow)

Chromatogram of robustness variation in flow rate – 1.0 mL/min

Chromatogram of robustness variation in flow rate – 1.4 mL/min

Robustness (change in the wavelength)

Chromatogram of robustness variation in wavelength 306 nm

Chromatogram of robustness variation in wavelength 310 nm

Parameter	Tinidazole		Ofloxacin	
	Retention time(min)	Tailing factor	Retention time(min)	Tailing factor
Flow				
1.0ml/min	2.930	1.444	4.907	1.308
1.2ml/min	2.213	1.409	3.740	1.219
1.4ml/min	1.780	1.368	2.980	1.185
Wavelength				
306 nm	2.203	1.409	3.707	1.219
308nm	2.213	1.409	3.740	1.219
310nm	2.223	1.364	3.710	1.219

Ruggedness

The ruggedness of the method was studied by the determining the analyst to analyst variation by performing the Assay by two different analysts

Acceptance criteria:

The % Relative standard deviation of Assay values between two analysts should be not more than 2.0%.

Chromatogram of Analyst 01 standard preparation

Chromatogram of Analyst 01 sample preparation

Chromatogram of Analyst 02 standard preparation

Chromatogram of Analyst 02 sample preparation

Results for Ruggedness

Tinidazole	%Assay	Ofloxacin	% Assay
Analyst 01	98.22	Analyst 01	99.63
Analyst 02	100.00	Analyst 02	100.63
%RSD(Rt)	0.22	%RSD(Rt)	0.11

Observation

From the observation the %RSD between two analysts Assay values not greater than 2.0%, hence the method was rugged.

DISCUSSION:

A basic and selective LC method was described for the determination of Ofloxacin and Tinidazole tablet

dosage forms. Chromatographic separation were achieved on a C₁₈ column utilizing mobile phase consisting of a mixture of 50 volumes of 20mM Phosphate buffer pH 3.5: 50 volumes of Acetonitrile, with detection of 308 nm. Linearity were detected in the range 30-70 µg /ml for Ofloxacin ($r^2 = 0.9992$) and 90-210 µg /ml for Tinidazole ($r^2 = 0.9972$) for the number of drugs estimated by the suggested methods were in good agreement with the label claim.

The proposed procedures were validated. The accuracy of the methods was assessed by recovery studies at three different levels. Recovery experiments indicated the absence of interference from usually encountered pharmaceutical additives. The method were found to be precise as indicated by the repeatability analysis, showing %RSD less than 2. All statistical data proves validity of the methods and can be utilizing for routine analysis of pharmaceutical dosage form.

CONCLUSION:

From the above experimental results and parameters it were concluded that, this novel developed method for the simultaneous estimation of Ofloxacin and Tinidazole were found to be simple, precise, accurate and high resolution and shorter retention time makes this process more acceptable and cost effective and it can be effectively applied for routine analysis in research institutions, quality control department in meant in industries, approved testing laboratories, bio-pharmaceutical and bio-equivalence studies and in clinical pharmacokinetic studies in near future.

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